

Unprecedented bloom of *Fibrocapsa japonica* on French coasts

Sources : Eurostat/Gisco, GéoBretagne, Ifremer - Projection : WGS84 / Pseudo-Mercator

Fig. 1. Map of the different bays in southern Brittany monitored as part of the REPHY program.

Since 1987, the REPHY (French Phytoplankton and Hydrology Monitoring Network in Coastal Waters), operated by IFREMER, has conducted long-term monitoring of phytoplankton species along the French coastline. Coupled since 2013 with the citizen science program Phenomer (<https://www.phenomer.org/>) [1], which aims to collect public reports of discoloured water events along the French coasts, these initiatives provide substantial spatial coverage and a high level of information for the study of blooms.

Between November 2025 and January 2026, samples collected as part of the REPHY monitoring program, together with reports of brown-coloured waters exhibiting visible mucilaginous aggregates, enabled IFREMER to detect a bloom of the raphidophyte *Fibrocapsa japonica* in southern Brittany (Fig 1). The observation of a bloom of such magnitude is unprecedented along the French coasts since the establishment of the REPHY monitoring program.

Twice a month, vertical profiles of various physicochemical parameters (temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen, fluorescence and turbidity) were collected throughout the entire water column at REPHY sampling stations. During routine samplings conducted at the “Men er Roué” station in Quiberon Bay and the “Concarneau large” station in Concarneau Bay (Fig. 1) on November 18, 2025, unusually high fluorescence peaks were recorded. Measurements recorded in Quiberon Bay on November 18, 2025 (Fig. 2) indicated a homogeneous water column in terms of both salinity and temperature, with values around 33 and 14 °C, respec-

tively, consistent with seasonal conditions. In contrast, unusually high fluorescence values were recorded in the upper few meters of the water column (0–4 m), reaching up to 35 FFU, indicating elevated chlorophyll-*a* concentration. This was confirmed by very high chlorophyll-*a* concentration measured in the subsurface sample (105.7 µg L⁻¹). These values decreased from 4 m depth to the seabed (–10 m), reflecting the presence of a surface bloom. This was consistent with elevated dissolved oxygen concentrations at the surface (~10.8 mg L⁻¹ at 1 m), which decreased along with fluorescence, indicating intense photosynthetic activity in surface waters. Turbidity values exhibited a similar pattern, suggesting a high load of suspended organic matter.

Light microscopy observations using the Utermöhl method revealed a bloom of *Fibrocapsa japonica* (Fig. 3) and molecular identification based on culture sequencing of D1-D3 region of the LSU rDNA gene, using D1r/D3b primers, confirmed the species. A bloom maximum was recorded in Quiberon Bay on 18 November 2025, reaching 4.8 x 10⁶ cells L⁻¹. REPHY monitoring further showed that the bloom persisted over a ten-week period and progressively migrated

northward up to the bay of Brest (Fig. 4). The northward displacement is most likely attributable to the persistent southerly winds in the area during this period. The geomorphology of Brittany, characterised by a succession of semi-enclosed bays and substantial riverine nutrient inputs, likely further supported bloom development. An unusually high abundance of *Karenia spp.* (mostly *Karenia mikimotoi*) was also recorded during the same period, reaching 3.3 x 10⁴ cells L⁻¹ in Quiberon Bay on November 18, 2025. Both *Fibrocapsa* and *Karenia* are classified by the French sanitary agency Anses as potential producers of brevetoxins (BTXs) [2], phycotoxins known to pose risks to shellfish consumers [3] and with toxic effects in marine fauna, including fish kills [4]. Chemical analyses, using an LC-MS/MS method developed within the EMERGTOX monitoring program for emerging marine toxins in shellfish [5], were therefore conducted on eight shellfish samples (pools of several individuals of blue mussels, *Mytilus spp.*, and Pacific oysters, *Magallana gigas*, separately) collected in Quiberon Bay and Morbihan Gulf. All thirteen targeted brevetoxins were below detection levels [6]. Additional screening for other *Karenia*-associated toxin families (tamulamides, brevisulcatic acids, gymnocins, brevisulcenals, brevisamide, brevenal, brevesin, and several brevetoxins not covered by the EMERGTOX method) also yielded negative results.

Fibrocapsa japonica, described in Japan in 1973 by Toriumi and Takano [7], was first reported along the French coasts in 1991 [8]. It has since been regularly observed, but this represents the first bloom of such magnitude in

Fig. 2. Vertical profile of physicochemical parameters recorded in Quiberon Bay on 18 November, 2025.

Fig. 3. Light microscope images of living *Fibrocapsa japonica* cells. Scale bars = 20 μm .

French waters. REPHY data [9] indicate that the previous maximum abundance occurred in 2013 in the Vilaine estuary, reaching 1.9×10^5 cells L^{-1} , approximately 25 times lower than values than maximum concentrations observed in 2025.

Although associated with fish mortality events in Japan in the 1970s [7], no mortality events were reported during this bloom period in France. Some fishermen nevertheless reported unusually low fish abundance in Concarneau Bay and the Morbihan Gulf. An important mortality event involving Atlantic puffins (*Fratercula arctica*) was also recorded in southern Brittany in the weeks following the bloom (February). While the successive storms that hit the region during this period appear to have been the primary cause of mortality, a reduction in fish availability — the puffins' main prey — linked to the bloom may have further weakened the birds, making them more vulnerable.

Fig. 5. Viability percentage (expressed relative to solvent control L1 medium at 25%) of fish gill cells (RTgill-W1 cell line), after two-hour exposure to different concentrations of crude intracellular fractions from the French *F. japonica* strain IFR-CC 25-055. Different letters indicate significant differences (ANOVA followed by Tukey HSD post-hoc test, $p < 0.05$, $n = 6$ replicate wells).

		South ← → North						
Year	Week	Vilaine estuary	Morbihan gulf	Quiberon bay	Lorient	Concarneau bay	Douarnenez bay	Brest bay
2025	47	1.5×10^5	2.5×10^5	4.8×10^6		3.4×10^5		
2025	48		1.3×10^5	8.0×10^5	1.5×10^5	2.4×10^5		
2025	49		2.6×10^5	1.8×10^5	3.7×10^4	1.1×10^5		
2025	50		8.5×10^4					
2025	51	200	6.3×10^4	6.2×10^3	6.5×10^4	5.4×10^5		
2025	52					5.3×10^4		
2026	02					300	2.4×10^5	
2026	03							2.3×10^4
2026	04					100	500	
2026	05							1.3×10^5
2026	07							2.2×10^4

Fig. 4. Temporal evolution of *F. japonica* abundances (cells L^{-1}) recorded at REPHY stations during the bloom (November 2025 to February 2026).

According to the Ligue pour la Protection des Oiseaux (LPO), 45,014 puffins were found beached along the French Atlantic coast between 19 December 2025 and 17 March 2026. This figure represents only a fraction of the total mortality, as experts estimate that only about one in ten birds reaches the shore [10]. *In vitro* bioassays were performed to assess the ichthyotoxic potential of a French strain (*F. japonica* IFR-CC 25-055), isolated from a single-cell from the bloom. Intracellular content, obtained from the supernatant of lysed culture pellets, were tested on the RTgill-W1 fish gill cell line (CRL-2523, ATCC), following Beesoo et al. [11] and Rolton et al. [12]. No significant cytotoxicity was observed between 4.0×10^5 to 6.2×10^6 cells L^{-1} (Fig. 5). A significant reduction in cell viability occurred only above 2.5×10^7 cells L^{-1} (Fig. 5). The maximum environmental concentration observed (4.8×10^6 cells L^{-1}) therefore suggests limited cytotoxic potential under natural conditions. By contrast, Aguiar Juárez et al. [13] reported cytotoxicity on RTgill-W1 for Argentinian strains of *F. japonica* at much lower cell densities, (6.2×10^5 cells L^{-1}), highlighting strain-dependent toxicity modulated by environmental and physiological factors such as salinity, temperature, light intensity and nutrient availability. While the French strain appears weakly toxic under tested conditions, further comparative studies are needed to assess variability among strains and growth conditions.

This event highlights the value of integrating fixed-station phytoplankton monitoring with citizen science observations for early detection of bloom events. It also demonstrates the importance of combining taxonomy, molecular biology, hydrology, chemistry and ecotoxicology for comprehensive characterisation of harmful algal events.

References

1. Siano R et al. 2020. Mar Policy 117: 103039. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2018.01.022>
2. Anses 2021. Saisine n 2020-SA-0020. <https://www.anses.fr/fr/system/files?file=ERCA2020SA0020Ra-b.pdf>
3. Kirkpatrick B et al. 2004. Harmful Algae 3(2):99–115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2003.08.005>
4. Lassus P et al. 2016. Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO. IOC Manuals and Guides, 68. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf00002477675>.
5. Amzil Z et al. 2026. Mar Drugs 24(2) : 67. doi.org/10.3390/md24020067.
6. Le Moigne M et al. 2025. Expertise Ifremer N° 25-079
7. Toriumi S & Takano H 1973. Bull Tokai Reg Fish Reg Lab 76:25–35.
8. Billard C 1992. Cryptogamie, Algologie 13(3):225–231.
9. REPHY 2023. REPHY dataset – SEANOE. doi.org/10.17882/47248.
10. France Info, 2026. Plus de 45 000 macareux échoués sur les plages de la côte atlantique cet hiver. Available at: https://www.franceinfo.fr/environnement/plus-de-45-000-macareux-echoues-sur-les-plages-de-la-cote-atlantique-cet-hiver_7934996.html
11. Beesoo R et al. 2025. Harmful Algae 150:102980. doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2025.102980.
12. Rolton A et al. 2025. Harmful Algae 150:102991. doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2025.102980
13. Aguiar Juárez D et al. 2025. Toxins 17(8):386. doi.org/10.3390/toxins17080386

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